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The hustle lifeways of Black women in mining-affected communities of South Africa

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ABSTRACT

This study sets out to investigate the lived experiences of Black women living in South African communities affected by mining, specifically exploring how they navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by large-scale resource extraction. To do so, the study introduces the concept of “hustle lifeways”. In the context of mining-affected communities, this term captures how small-scale, often informal, income-generating activities are embodied in Black women’s experiences of large-scale mining. Data is collected through a three-months fieldwork period across six mining-affected communities located in different provinces of South Africa. Thematic analysis highlights three key dimensions of hustle lifeways, namely survival, autonomy and caregiving responsibilities. The analysis of these three themes evidences Black women’s resourcefulness, while underscoring the numerous challenges posed to them by large-scale mining, particularly in terms of exclusion, heightened uncertainty and increased care work. The insights from this analysis contribute to the literature on mining and women in South Africa, which has predominantly focused on women employed in the sector, by offering a new perspective on the gendered dimensions of large-scale mining.

1. Introduction

Historically, large-scale mining has played a central role in South Africa’s economic development. Throughout much of the twentieth century, the industry has represented a driving force behind the country’s industrial revolution, attracting substantial investments and spurring the growth of new mining towns (Cole and Broadhurst, 2020; Fedderke and Pirouz, 2002; Marais et al., 2018). At its peak, revenues from mineral extraction contributed about 20% of the country’s total GDP (Fedderke and Pirouz, 2002; Statistics South Africa, 2015). Although the industry’s prominence has declined in recent years, large-scale mining continues to be an important industry in resource-rich areas, where it remains a key source of business and employment (Cock, 2019).

Despite the considerable wealth that large-scale mining has generated and still generates in South Africa, the industry has been linked to numerous issues which disproportionately affect local communities, contributing to the emergence of what Hargreaves (2016, p. 145)

describes as “an acute, multifaceted social, economic and environmental crisis”.

In townships exposed to the direct and indirect effects of this sector – or, as they will be henceforth referred to, “mining-affected communities”, Black, working-class women in particular struggle to survive.

While playing an active role in the (inter)national extractivist “project” (Tsing, 2015, p. 21), these women have been so far under-recognized in both academic and policy debates (Jenkins, 2014; WoMin, 2020). In the literature on women and mining, for instance, much of the focus has been on documenting women’s involvement in mining activities (Benya, 2016; Gier & Mercier (2006); Lahiri-Dutt and Macintyre, 2006). Numerous studies now exist on the experiences of women artisanal miners or, like in the case of South Africa, women working in industrial mines (Benya, 2017; Botha and Cronjé, 2015a; Botha, 2016; Buss et al., 2019; Jenkins, 2014; Lahiri-Dutt, 2022; Ofosu et al., 2022; Pugliese, 2021). By contrast, comparatively little attention has been given to women living in mining-affected communities without being necessarily employed in the sector. Available studies on this group

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are limited and have predominantly addressed the disproportionate impacts of mining on women, with far fewer exploring these women's lived experiences as agents, particularly regarding their livelihood strategies (Collis, 1999; Eftimie et al., 2009; Jenkins, 2014, 2017; Mahy, 2011; Sinclair, 2021. Collis, 1999).

In spite of their under-recognition, this study argues that understanding the lived experiences of Black, working-class women living in mining-affected communities are of critical importance. At a time when large-scale removal of natural resources shows no signs of abating, despite well-documented consequences for people and the environment, probing issues of justice and sustainability becomes paramount. This study argues that the perspective of these South African women can present us with a much needed, critical viewpoint over long-standing discussions on extractivism, here defined as a model of wealth accumulation by means of resource extraction, and development (Pereira and Tsikata, 2021). They show us "what else is going on" (Tsing, 2015, p. 61) at the "unruly edges" (p. 20), after multinational corporations have come to local communities like "giant bulldozers" (p. 61) and seemingly "flattened the earth to its specifications" (ibid.).

Central to the stories of the Black, working-class women in South Africa is "hustling", or the practice of engaging in one or more small-scale, often informal, income-generating activities. Typical examples of a hustle include distributing and selling small items (e.g. air fresheners, beauty products, herbal teas), cooking and cleaning for others, and running day cares. These activities are particularly important to Black working-class women¹ because they provide them with the means to sustain themselves and their families amidst the precarious living conditions generated and/or exacerbated by large-scale extraction of mineral resources. Inspired by Fisher et al. (2017, 2021), this study conceptualizes hustling as a "lifeway" – or, according to Tsing's definition (2015), a "way of being" (p. 23) that emerges from encounters between the human and the non-human. In the context of mining-affected communities, this concept captures how the practice of hustling is embodied in Black, working-class women's lived experiences of large-scale resource extraction.

Using hustle lifeways as a lens, this study sets out to explore the multiple and dynamic ways in which Black, working-class women navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by large-scale mining in their communities. The analysis draws on data collected during a three-months fieldwork period across six mining-affected communities in different provinces of South Africa, using a combination of semi-structure interviews, participant observation, focus group discussions and site visits. Through a thematic analysis approach, three central themes of hustle lifeways are identified: survival, autonomy, and caregiving responsibilities.

The three themes provide key insights into Black, working-class women's lived experiences of large-scale resource extraction, underscoring their resourcefulness while highlighting the significant challenges that the sector poses to them. These challenges include, in particular, exclusion, uncertainty and increased burden of care work. The findings offer an alternative perspective to discussions of mining-driven development in South Africa, emphasizing the persistence of gendered hardships despite policy efforts to address inequalities within the sector.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 provides insights into the significance of mining in South Africa and discusses women's historical role in South Africa's mining industry. Section 3 reviews the relevant literature on women and mining. Section 4 describes the methodology employed in this study, while Section 5 presents the results. Section 6 is the discussion and Section 7 is the conclusion.

¹ Black women in this research are described as working-class to the extent that their livelihoods, and the livelihoods of people close to them, rely on precarious income-generating activities, whether low-wage work or hustling.

2. Background

2.1. The history of mining in South Africa

The exploitation of mineral resources has profoundly shaped the development trajectory of South Africa. According to Davenport (2013: p. 1), "nowhere else in the world has a mineral revolution proven so influential in weaving the political, economic and social fabric of a society". Understanding South Africa's history of extractivism is therefore essential to contextualize the hustle lifeways of today's Black, working-class women living in mining-affected communities. This section turns to provide insights into the influence of mining in South Africa over the last hundred years.

South Africa boasts some of the world's greatest known reserves of gold, diamonds, manganese and platinum-group metals (PGMs), as well as sizeable deposits of coal, iron ore, chromium and vanadium (Yager, 2023; Taylor et al., 2005). Since the discovery of this incredible mineral wealth in the nineteenth century, the mining industry has represented the "locomotive" (Fedderke and Pirouz, 2002, p.1) of South Africa's rapid industrial revolution, propelling economic growth, and spurring the development of mining towns and cities (Cole and Broadhurst, 2020; Marais et al., 2018). Gold mining in particular has played an important role in the economy of British and Boers administration, and later under the Union of South Africa, generating enormous wealth and fostering the development of the city of Johannesburg (Harrison and Zack, 2012).

If resource extraction has been key to the economic development of South Africa, it has also created numerous problems. The expansion of the mining sector, facilitated by exploitative labor structures, has, in fact, been linked to a widening of class, race and gender inequalities (Fine and Rustomjee, 1997; Wilson, 2001). This becomes particularly evident when considering the system of oscillating migration on which mines have relied until the late 1900s. Under said system, Black men from neighboring African countries were recruited to work in the South African mines, housed in single-sex compounds, and forced to return home at the end of their short-term contract (Van der Merwe et al., 2010; Wilson, 2001, 2011). This enabled companies to pay lower wages, control their workforce, and avoid obligations to invest in local communities (Wilson, 2011). The Marikana Massacre of 2012, when 34 striking miners were killed by the South African Police Service, showcases the enduring tensions that these practices have originated within the industry (Twala, 2012).

Further deepening inequalities, the practices developed in the mining industry have laid the foundation for the racially and gender segregated labor system of the apartheid regime (Smalberger, 1976; Wilson, 2001, 2011). This is the system that has led to the creation of townships, designated as dormitory settlements for Non-White workers, where the majority of Black people still live and where fieldwork for this study took place. Today, these areas remain significantly poorer than historically white neighborhood, concentrating 60 % of the country's unemployed population, and face a considerable number of challenges, including lack of adequate services, degrading infrastructure, and violent crime (Mahajan, 2014; du Toit et al., 2018). In mining regions, these communities are also the most vulnerable to the devastating environmental and health consequences of resource extraction (Cronjé and Chenga, 2007; Pretty and Odeku, 2017).

Even if in recent years the significance of the industry has decreased, with some sectors like gold steadily declining, and the country has agreed to take steps to reduce its reliance on coal, mining remains extremely relevant to modern-day South Africa (Minerals Council of South Africa, 2019). Particularly in mining regions, local economies are often still centered around large-scale resource extraction, with multinational companies representing major business hubs and a primary source of employment (Cock, 2019). As this model of economic development persists, however, so do the challenges associated with its exploitative practices. Despite policy efforts to redress historical inequalities, notably through the introduction of Social and Labor Plans

(SLPs) which require companies to invest in local communities, many issues remain (Cole and Broadhurst, 2020). In resource-rich regions, in fact, mining companies continue to draw vast amounts of resources with very little beneficiation for local communities, and particularly women within them, contributing to the emergence of what Hargreaves (2016, p. 145) describes as “an acute, multifaceted social, economic and environmental crisis”.

2.2. Women and mining: a history of the edges

Positioning women in South Africa’s history of extractivism presents several challenges. Women, in fact, have been formally excluded from the mining sector until 1996, when the prohibition to employ female miners for underground work was eventually lifted, and their contributions, either through informal mine labor, unpaid reproductive work or service provisions, have long been neglected (Botha and Cronjé, 2015a). Very little is thus known about the role that women played in the expansion of the mining industry, as well as their personal perspectives and experiences of this period of rapid political, economic and social transformation.

Challenging the mainstream construction of mining as an inherently “masculine” or “male” space, the limited literature available tells us that, while women have been sidelined throughout the mineral revolution, they have nonetheless been present and active in and around mines. In Moodie’s (1994) description of a gold mining town, for instance, women can be found working as saloon managers, beer brewers and sellers, and sex workers. Later accounts situate women directly in the mines, providing services as cooks, cleaners and nurses (Benya, 2016; Breckenridge, 1998). In some cases, like asbestos mining, data shows that women have also participated in the sector as miners in their own rights, representing a substantial share of the mines’ workforce (McCulloch, 2003).

Even if their involvement in South Africa’s history of mining is likely understated, it is undeniable that women, and particularly Black women, have faced significant exclusion. Throughout the nineteenth and most of the twentieth century, in fact, the country’s labor market has been strongly segregated by race and gender. As a result, Black women have been long confined to a narrow range of occupations, mostly within agriculture and domestic service (Alexander, 2007; Cock, 1987). During apartheid, this confinement has been enforced by means of pass laws, which prevented many of them from leaving rural areas and enjoying the economic benefits of urbanization (Savage, 1986). Already banned from underground work, these restrictions on Black women’s “urbanization” have further limited their ability to seek employment in the burgeoning mining industry (Sesele et al., 2021a).

The consequences of Black women’s systematic exclusion from South Africa’s mining industry, at a time when the sector represented the backbone of the economy, have been far reaching. Today, Black women are more likely to be living in poverty and struggling to find stable employment than any other population groups, especially in rural areas (Phaswana, 2021). They are also disproportionately burdened by house and care work within their communities, which limits their ability to integrate labor markets and increases their vulnerability to economic (e.g. COVID-19) and environmental shocks (Bak, 2008; Chitiga et al., 2022). In addition, Black women’s socio-economic marginalization exposes them to crime and gender-based violence, which represent some of the most severe issues affecting their communities (Enaifoghe et al., 2021).

Despite efforts to increase female participation in mining, notably through quotas set in the latest version of the Mining Charter, Black women’s involvement in the industry remains low compared to men (Minerals Council of South Africa, 2020). This is typically attributed to the physical intensity of some mining jobs, notorious health and safety issues, and a “masculine” work culture characterized, for instance, by widespread sexual harassment (Benya, 2017; Botha and Cronjé, 2015b; Botha, 2016). In areas of resource extraction, where mining represents

the main industry and source of employment, these issues perpetuate gendered socio-economic inequalities.

3. Literature review

The concept of gender in development emerged in the 1970s with the Women in Development (WID) approach, which sought to reshape women’s role in the economy and tackle the social causes of inequality between men and women (Sesele et al., 2021b). Criticized for its focus on white middle-class women, in the 1980s, WID was later replaced by the Gender and Development (GAD) approach. GAD shifted the attention to broader issues of intersectionality, emphasizing the importance of race, class, ethnicity and colonial history in shaping women’s experiences of oppression in the international economic order (Lahiri-Dutt, 2011). Building on this approach, this study focuses on the experiences of Black, working-class women as a distinct group within mining-affected communities.

Within this broader literature, the present study belongs to the growing body of research aiming to give visibility to women’s bodies, roles, and challenges in mining (Benya, 2016). This literature started with the seminal works of Gier and Mercier (2006), and Lahiri-Dutt and Macintyre (2006), which challenged common perceptions of women as peripheral actors in mining economies, and drew scholars’ attention to issues of gender in extractive industries (Benya, 2016). Since then, numerous studies have been published on women and mining, exploring their lived experiences across developed and developing countries, artisanal and industrial mining operations, formal and informal activities, different sizes and types of mineral deposits, from both an historical and contemporary perspective (Lahiri-Dutt, 2011).

Within this literature, most studies have focused on the category of women “in” mining, defined by direct involvement in the extraction, processing and transportation of minerals. As female participation in artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM) has been on the rise, a significant share of this research is dedicated, in particular, to the challenges and opportunities of women artisanal miners. Numerous topics have been addressed. These include gendered divisions of labor, the evolution of gendered identities and emotions, the gendered effects of policy interventions, such as formalization schemes, as well as women’s specific health and safety risks, barriers to entry and difficulties in advancement (Benya, 2017; Buss et al., 2019; Jenkins, 2014; Lahiri-Dutt, 2022; Ofosu et al., 2022; Pugliese, 2021). This study connects with this strand of literature to the extent that mining in its artisanal form is part of hustle lifeways in mining-affected communities of South Africa.

Women “around” mines, who experience the direct and indirect consequences of extractive industries, without necessarily being employed in them, have received less attention (WoMin, 2020). Studies concerned with this category of women are, in fact, fewer and predominantly focused on the gendered impacts of mining. For however limited, this strand of research has contributed valuable insights, evidencing inequalities in the distribution of the costs and benefits of resource extraction. Findings show, in fact, that women are disproportionately vulnerable to land degradation, pollution, violence and displacement due to traditional gender roles that hold them responsible for house (e.g. collecting water, preparing food) and care work (e.g. assisting ill or disabled family members) (Eftimie et al., 2009; Jenkins, 2014; Sinclair, 2021). In addition, women are found to be the ones to benefit the least from resource extraction. Evidence shows that women are often remunerated less and excluded from communities’ negotiations with mining companies (Jenkins, 2014).

Even when mines close, women are found to be disproportionately affected. In South Africa, Sesele et al. (2021b) evidence how the decline of the mining industry has further reduced opportunities for women, while simultaneously increasing their responsibilities in the household. While there is room for local institutions to mitigate some of these negative consequences, authors like Sesele et al. (2021a) have evidence the absence of a policy link between closure and women.

Moving beyond a passive construction of women “around” mines, a recent line of work has brought to the fore their contributions to anti-mining activism. This research investigates women’s choices and strategies in navigating conflicts with large-scale mines, as well as within communities, highlighting their agency and power. [Jenkins \(2017\)](#), for instance, documents how women’s opposition to resource extraction in rural Peru and Ecuador manifests in everyday acts of resistance centered around narratives of “staying put” and “carrying on”. Outside of activism, however, little is still known about the active role played by those women who, while not employed in the mines, still participate in, contribute to and shape mining economies. The few available studies discuss women’s negotiation of male power within marital relationships ([Collis, 1999](#)), and sex work ([Mahy, 2011](#)), but do not extensively address their livelihood strategies vis-à-vis resource extraction. In another study, [Kolen et al. \(2018\)](#) on settlement and movement of small-scale gold mining communities, women included, in the Amazon.

More research is therefore needed on how women negotiate and perceive mining, and particularly large-scale operations, within their communities. This is the case in South Africa as well, where the literature has broadly followed the same trends. Studies on the South African mining industry have focused on the challenges faced by women in industrial mines ([Benya, 2017](#); [Botha and Cronjé, 2015a](#); [Botha, 2016](#)), and the gendered impacts of large-scale resource extraction ([González et al., 2021](#); [Sesele et al., 2021b](#); [Shackleton, 2020](#)). They have also discussed the ramifications of gender policies. [Kaggwa \(2020\)](#), for instance, emphasizes the important role of policy and local government, while emphasizing their limits. In their analysis of gender sensitive policies in the mining sector, in fact, they show that legislation can be useful to mitigate challenges for women in the workplace and reduce gender inequality, but it is not sufficient by itself.

Only very recently, interest in women and artisanal mining has risen ([de Theije and Heemskerk, 2009](#); [Kassa, 2022](#)). Little to no information is, instead, available on the lived experiences and “world-making projects” ([Tsing, 2015](#), p. 22) of Black, working-class women living in mining-affected communities in South Africa.

4. Methodology

The present research relies on data collected during a three-months fieldwork period, and across multiple provinces of South Africa. During the spring of 2023, six townships were visited in Gauteng, Northern Cape, Free State, Mpumalanga and Limpopo provinces. Each township neighbored at least one large-scale mineral deposit at an advanced stage of production, and had made direct or indirect experience of its extractive activities. The type of mineral(s) extracted varied, but included gold, manganese, coal and platinum. All fieldwork sites were visited once for several days, during which the researchers participate into day to day community activities. Only one township located in Merafong City Local Municipality received a second visit. The geographical distribution of the sites is displayed in [Fig. 1](#). Markers correspond to the location of the local or metropolitan municipality.

Communities were accessed through collaboration with the South African civil society organization MACUA / WAMUA. Established in the aftermath of the Marikana Massacre, MACUA / WAMUA mobilizes men, women and youth in townships negatively affected by mining. The organization comprises a wide network of decentralized branches, spread across the country. In each location, members advocate for their community’s specific needs by engaging multinational companies and institutions. Tapping into this network, fieldwork sites were selected from the pool of active MACUA / WAMUA branches.

The selection of fieldwork sites was guided by both logistical considerations and the analytical objective of enabling comparisons across different mining sectors and the urban/rural divide. Specifically, the selection includes locations that represent three distinct sectoral trajectories. Three mining-affected communities are linked to gold mining, which has experienced a long and steady decline in South Africa. One is located next to coal mining, which has been agreed to be gradually phased out in the coming years. The remaining two communities, instead, are located next to manganese and platinum mining, which are striving to attract new investments as the demand for critical minerals increases. For more details on the characteristics of each fieldwork site, see [Table 1](#).

Fig. 1. Map of fieldwork sites in South Africa.

Table 1
Description of fieldwork sites in South Africa.

Municipality	Province	Mineral	Urban / Rural	Reported Impacts
Merafong City Local Municipality	Gauteng I	Gold	Urban	Severe air pollution leading to respiratory problems and illnesses (e.g. silicosis); water pollution; sinkholes; crime and violence.
City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality	Gauteng II	Gold	Urban	Severe air pollution leading to respiratory problems and illnesses (e.g. silicosis); water pollution.
Matjhabeng Local Municipality	Free State	Gold	Rural	Severe air pollution leading to respiratory problems and illnesses (e.g. silicosis); water pollution.
Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality	Northern Cape	Manganese	Rural	Severe air and water pollution leading to manganese toxicity; land degradation.
Emalahleni Local Municipality	Mpumalanga	Coal	Rural	Severe air and water pollution; blasting; noise pollution from extractive activities.
Mogalakwena Local Municipality	Limpopo	Platinum	Rural	Land grabbing and loss of access to clean drinking water; social tensions.

Note: Information reported in this table reflects the characteristics of fieldwork sites and experiences of mining impacts as reported by research participants during fieldwork (March – May 2023).

When integrating data from multiple sites, the main challenge was addressing the specificities of each fieldwork site's socio-economic, political and cultural context, which shapes the lived experiences of community members in distinct ways. This heterogeneity represented a source of richness in the data, but also required careful consideration during the analysis.

In each township, research participants were selected based on a sequential approach, alternating purposive and snowball sampling with gender and age (+18) as inclusion criteria (Bryman, 2016). The resulting sample is primarily composed of Black South African women between the age of 20 and 75. Here, it is important to acknowledge that research participants were identified and contacted by leveraging the network of MACUA / WAMUA members. The potential biases that this sampling strategy may have captured were reflected upon in the data analysis process and taken into account in the writing of this article. A more detailed description of the sample composition is provided in Table 2.

Methodologically, this study relies on an ethnographic approach. Primary methods used include interviews and participant observation, with additional information gathered through focus group discussions and site visits. During each stay in a township, the choice of method used was based on the prevailing circumstances and the specific research objectives. When engaging with the artisanal miners, for instances, visits to their mining site were preferred over focus group discussions, as

Table 2
Description of sample composition.

Municipality	Participants	Women	Age	Activities
Merafong City Local Municipality	25	21	20 - 75	Interviews; focus group discussions; site visit.
City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality	22	17	25 - 70	Interviews; focus group discussions; site visit.
Matjhabeng Local Municipality	10	10	25 - 60	Focus group discussions; workshops.
Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality	15	15	25 - 60	Interviews, focus group discussions; workshops.
Emalahleni Local Municipality	10	10	25 - 75	Focus group discussions.
Mogalakwena Local Municipality	3	3	30 - 60	Workshops; site visits.

Note: This table only account for research participants which were either interviewed or part of a focus group discussion. It does not include interactions during site visits and workshops. Age ranges are estimated based on information relayed by research participants.

deemed more efficient to learn about their livelihood strategies. Interviews and focus groups discussions were led with a flexible interview guide, primarily composed of open-end question, leaving margin for participants to expand on their own reflections, and to raise issues they deemed relevant. The questions were designed to prompt the respondents to provide background information on themselves (e.g. marital status, occupation, etc...) as well as to reflect on a number of topics, including: the challenges faced by members of their communities, opportunities in the mining sector, notions of female empowerment and more. Most interactions with research participants took place in English. However, several occasions required translation support from either a research participant or a member of MACUA / WAMUA. While some nuances may have been inevitably lost in translation, limiting participation in this study to English speakers would have resulted in the exclusion of specific perspectives and diversity loss.

Information was noted down throughout fieldwork and later analyzed using a thematic approach. This involved careful review of all information gathered to identify recurring themes or patterns.

4.1. Ethical considerations

This research project is committed to the current standards of accountability and responsibility as defined in [Rauhala and Kalokairinou \(2021\)](#). All participants have given their free, prior and informed consent, following an explanation on the nature, scope and expected outcomes of fieldwork. Their anonymity has been ensured through the attribution of pseudonyms and the withholding of any information that could lead to identification. This is the reason why, for instance, this study only refers to the names of the local municipalities in which the communities are located, rather than the names of the townships or communities themselves.

Moving beyond “do no harm”, the present project has been developed based on the principle that research should be a mutually beneficial process ([Mackenzie et al., 2007](#)). All research collaborators were compensated for their time and efforts, according to rates established in agreement with the advice office of MACUA / WAMUA. Research activities and questions were selected to respond to collaborators' needs and interests. Ultimately, the project has been developed with the intention to create a research output that is valuable for local struggles by enhancing the visibility of communities', and particularly women's, challenges.

The risks of unequal power dynamics with research participants, but also with members of MACUA / WAMUA, were thoroughly examined and discussed throughout the entire duration of fieldwork ([Brinkmann](#)

and Kvale, 2005). These reflections felt particularly relevant given the researcher's positionality as a White European researcher within the racialized context of South Africa (Sultana, 2007). Crucial has been, in this regard, the involvement of key representatives from MACUA / WAMUA in the design of the project through a practice which some have described as "co-laboring" (Fisher et al., 2023). Their insightful comments and feedback have not only improved the overall quality of this research, but also contributed towards the implementation of a more context-sensitive process.

5. Findings

Data analysis reveals three central themes in the hustle lifeways of Black women in mining-affected communities: (i) survival, (ii) autonomy, and (iii) caregiving responsibility. These themes offer valuable insights into how women navigate the intersecting challenges and opportunities posed by large-scale mining in their communities. This section provides an in-depth examination of each of these themes.

5.1. Women *zama zama*

To women who participated in this research, hustling represents first and foremost an important source of livelihoods that allows them and their families to survive amidst the precarious living conditions of mining-affected communities.

Throughout fieldwork, research participants have repeatedly described women's role in the household as that of "breadwinners". In their usage, the term reflects women's key contribution to the survival of the family by ensuring that everyone's basic needs, but particularly those of the children, are met. This does not imply that women are the sole, or even the main, providers of the family. Other members can, and do, contribute wherever possible. They are not held responsible, however, the same way women feel they are.

"Women are the breadwinners. We are responsible for the family. We are the ones that have to provide for the children"²

Fulfilling the role of breadwinners in a context of widespread poverty and unemployment, as that of the mining-affected communities included in this research, can be exceptionally challenging. Women participants report that there are very few jobs in their area, and many of them are offered by the mines, where getting a position is notoriously difficult. "[Mining] companies prefer to hire men", some of them claim, "we are the breadwinners though!"

All women in this research agree that employment opportunities at the mines are particularly hard to access. Most positions, they say, are advertised for people 35 years old or younger, cutting many of them out from the eligible age bracket. Even when they have the "right" age, however, women still lack the required education to work in mining. "Skills are a big issue" a woman states during a workshop in Limpopo province.³ Her community is located next to a large platinum deposit, which is rumored it will attract new foreign investments. "We are not trained to work in the mines. Mines say they are sponsoring trainings, but for who? And where? We never see it; we never know about it", she tells the crowd.

Alongside eligibility, corruption and discrimination represent significant barriers. Across different communities, women report that it is not possible to find a job on the mines without exchanging sexual favors. In our conversations, many of them have mentioned the payment of what they call a "sex bribe" as one of the main reasons they don't work in mining.

"My husband doesn't want me to work in the mine. I think he knows that if I want to work there, I have to pay a sex bribe ... and it's not something you pay once. Every time the man wants you to sleep with him, you have to or you lose your job"⁴

The practice feels all the more daunting to some women as engaging in it can have serious consequences. Among them, in fact, mine employees are known for refusing to wear condoms. Paying a sex bribe therefore means incurring the risk of contracting HIV or falling pregnant⁵.

Piling up on complaints regarding corruption, are those about discrimination. "Women are lazy – that's what they say about us at the mines", a woman claims during a focus group discussion in Free State province⁶. "They think we go there just to get pregnant", another continues during the same conversation. One of their friends contributes with her own experience: "Mines don't want to hire plus size women".

Without prospects of getting a salaried job in mining, women in this research are left with little other employment opportunities, and have to find alternative ways of providing for their families. These usually imply a combination of state grants, like unemployment benefits and child support grant, as well as hustles.

"Women *zama*⁷ a lot. We don't work but we hustle all the time because state grants are not enough"⁸

Women's hustles look like any activity that can generate money. These include distributing house cleaning products, but also baking, braiding, housekeeping and babysitting. The majority of these activities are informal and run from home, but can generate steady, although typically small, revenues.

In some cases, women's hustles capitalize on the presence of large-scale mining. This is true, for instance, of a respondent whom shall be called Lesego Kunutu⁹. Lesego is a very determined woman who has high hopes for her children.¹⁰ Providing for them, she declares, is what makes her wake up every day. Lesego sells fast food to her community in City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, and has long planned to expand her business. Given the wealth of the local mining company, she has turned to them for capital to achieve her goal. Her request, however, has been quickly dismissed. Since her first failed attempt, Lesego has taken a business workshop at the local mine. With the knowledge she has acquired, she is now planning to register her fast food shop as a MSME. In this way, she states during her interview, she can apply to become a vendor for the mine. "It's always a struggle" she says, "but at the end of the day it's all about mindset". Lesego is convinced that, if she believes in her dream, it will happen. "An empire doesn't get built in one day", she states.

While Lesego has decided to approach the mining company directly, other women make money in their backyards. Ma Ntuli, for instance, has hustled for many years at the gates of a platinum mine. Every month on pay day, she would make her way there to sell small items to miners leaving their shift.¹¹ One day, after a workshop in Limpopo, she expresses frustration over the little number of jobs that the mines have

⁴ Interview with woman, Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality, 17 April 2023.

⁵ Focus group discussion with women, Matjhabeng Local Municipality, 05 May 2023.

⁶ Focus group discussion with women, Matjhabeng Local Municipality, 05 May 2023.

⁷ Term in isiZulu. Women participants explained that it translates to "trying something". Artisanal miners are also commonly referred to as "zama zamas".

⁸ Focus group discussion with women, Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality, 18 April 2023.

⁹ To guarantee anonymity, all respondents have been given pseudonyms. Names are based on the characters of a popular South African soap-opera called "Skeem Saam".

¹⁰ Interview, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 02 April 2023.

¹¹ Site visit to platinum mine, Mogalakwena Local Municipality, 23 May 2023.

² Focus group discussion with women, Matjhabeng Local Municipality, 05 May 2023.

³ Woman in MACUA / WAMUA workshop, Mogalakwena Local Municipality, 23 May 2023.

created in her community. According to her, companies prefer to outsource most of their services to large businesses in town. “Even laundry”, she complains. This leaves no opportunities to people like her.

Similarly, in Gauteng province, a group of resolute women walks every day to a mining dump in search of gold among the waste of large corporations.¹² The women wear basic protection gear, like rubber gloves and boots, and carry household items repurposed as work tools. They wash gravel and crush rocks for little amounts of gold, which they then sell on the black market where most profits are made by buyers. The women complain that they benefit less than what is fair, but enough to “buy bread every day”. Some of them are pushing to formalize their operations, as it would allow them to sell through legal channels and take out credit. Obtaining a license, however, has proven very difficult because of financial and administrative hurdles.

5.2. A hustle of one's own

Along with survival, autonomy is also a key theme in hustle lifeways. There are very few things, in fact, that women in this research feel they can rely on in their everyday life. Although insecurity and uncertainty are not unique to mining-affected communities, their stories suggest that large-scale resource extraction exacerbates these issues.

In one of the communities in Gauteng, gold mining has been particularly disruptive to people and the environment. The little stream where community members used to fish, for instance, has been polluted by the mines' toxic waste, depriving them of a crucial source of livelihoods. “[Before], even if unemployed, people could still put food on the table”, a woman from the community explains, “now all the fish are dead”¹³. Through underground blasting, gold mining has also contributed to the formation of sinkholes. Wide and deep, these sinkholes have swallowed entire portions of roads and buildings across the community. Several families have been forced to leave their homes, some of which they have worked hard to build. One man, encountered during the second visit to the community, is particularly vocal about his frustrations in this regard.¹⁴ A large sinkhole has opened right next to his house, and he has even hurt himself falling into it one night, but he refuses for his family to move. He explains that he has worked all his life to build a home, expand it and make it comfortable. He does not want to leave it.

In the same community, gold mining has also been disruptive to local education systems, as a massive sinkhole has opened in the courtyard of a school, leading part of the building to collapse. According to the school, the sinkhole has appeared from one day to the other, and only by pure luck no one has gotten hurt¹⁵. Since then, however, the students have been forced to follow classes in temporary structures just outside the perimeter. As the structures are not large enough for all them, grades have had to take turns. Based on what the school keeper knows, there is no official timeline for when the students will be able to safely access the school infrastructure again.

As part of South Africa's license application process, mining companies are legally required to submit Social and Labor Plans (SLPs) detailing their contributions to the development of local communities. Contributions can include upgrading or expanding local infrastructure, providing healthcare and education services, or supplying goods that community members need. From the perspective of women in this research, however, SLPs do little to improve the well-being of local

¹² Site visit to artisanal mining site, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 03 April 2023.

¹³ Informal conversation with WAMUA coordinator, Merafong City Local Municipality, 23 March 2023.

¹⁴ Informal conversation with man, Merafong City Local Municipality, 17 May 2023.

¹⁵ Site visit with WAMUA coordinator, Merafong City Local Municipality, 25 March 2023.

residents, or even just to compensate for the impacts of resource extraction, like the sinkholes just described. “We have to stand up for ourselves because the mines are not doing anything”, one of the women states during a focus group discussion.¹⁶ “The mine is draining. [...] They don't care”, laments another.¹⁷

During her interview, a woman named Koko Mantsha says that she “doesn't feel ok”¹⁸ about the relationship between mines and the community. Because of the noxious fumes generated by the processing of minerals in her community, she has spent considerable resources seeking medical attention for her children when they were little. “It was hard”, she says, “I decided to take them at the clinic in town because the local one built by the mine doesn't work right”. When asked to elaborate, she describes the local clinic as understaffed, and employing less competent nurses who wouldn't “even” acknowledge the fumes as a potential cause of illness. She recalls that, at the time, the company used to donate milk cartons to local residents. It wasn't much, and certainly not enough to mitigate the health damages caused by the fumes, but to her it was helpful when her children had the flu. Then, one day, she has suddenly stopped receiving milk. Ultimately, she states, facing the impacts of resource extraction and the unreliability of mining companies has taught her the importance of autonomy, which she seeks through hustling. “I don't depend on the government or anyone else. I can hustle and make my own money”, she states proudly.

To fully grasp the detrimental effects of mining on Black women's insecurity – and the inadequacy of corporate efforts to mitigate them – it is crucial to recognize their heightened vulnerability within these communities, which underscores the critical importance of autonomy in hustle lifeways. This vulnerability becomes particularly apparent in women's accounts of their experiences of motherhood which, for many of them, is described as a lonely struggle. Indeed, most women in this study report a profound lack of support from both personal networks and welfare state systems throughout pregnancy and child rearing.

Men, in particular, are generally considered to be unreliable by women in this research. “Men are scammers”, a woman in Northern Cape said during a focus group discussion¹⁹. “Men look good on the outside, but they are bad on the inside”, has commented another in the same occasion²⁰. “They don't care” has added a third²¹. Across communities, this type of complaints typically shares the same motive: men abandon them and neglect their fatherly responsibilities, leaving women alone to raise their children with severe consequences for their present and future prospects. “[Men] will give you babies and then leave you, only to come back when the babies are already old”²².

Without reliable support from the fathers of their children, many women in this research turn to their families for help. Not all families, however, prove to be equally dependable. In the case of Pretty Seakamela, the unreliability of her relatives has played an important role in her life decisions, including that of not having children. Pretty has, in fact, decided to break the “poverty cycle”²³ in her family and started her artisanal mining hustle to achieve her goal. Meanwhile, however, she must avoid accidental pregnancies. While some women can fall back on

¹⁶ Focus group discussion with men and women, Merafong City Local Municipality, 23 March 2023.

¹⁷ Interview with woman, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 02 April 2023.

¹⁸ Interview, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 02 April 2023.

¹⁹ Focus group discussion with women, Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality, 18 April 2023.

²⁰ Focus group discussion with women, Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality, 18 April 2023.

²¹ Focus group discussion with women, Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality, 18 April 2023.

²² Focus group discussion with women, Matjhabeng Local Municipality, 05 May 2023.

²³ Interview with woman artisanal miner, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 31 March 2023.

their families, in fact, Pretty knows this has never been an option for her. Growing up without her parents, she had a hard time affording everything she needed. One day, she remembers asking some family members for money to buy her school uniform. None of them agreed to help her out. "I can't trust them", Pretty states, referring to her relatives. "Families are the first ones to hold us back", she concludes.

Alone in their task of providing for their children, state grants could provide these single mothers with an important safety net. The money is, however, not enough to cover for a family's most basic needs. From the perspective of women in this research, this makes state support ultimately unreliable, reinforcing their need for autonomy.

"I am independent. If my husband divorces me, I can still take care of my kids. I know that I can't rely on social grants"²⁴

This is exemplified by the experience of Nozipho Mogotsi, a single mother of three, who has started various hustles as state grants alone are insufficient to make ends meet. "I receive grants for my two youngest children, but the money is insufficient and does not cover even the most basic needs. I am forced to prioritize, which is challenging," Nozipho shared during her first interview.²⁵ "This year, I couldn't afford to buy school ties." Initially selling hair products, she has since taken on other roles, including working as an enumerator for a market research company. Like many women in mining-affected communities, Nozipho's hustling is essential for navigating the insecurity and uncertainty that characterize her daily life.

5.3. The balancing act between livelihood and care

The challenges experienced by women in this research as a result of limited livelihood opportunities, mining impacts and unreliable support systems, are further compounded by their gendered responsibilities. Navigating these responsibilities is integral part of hustle lifeways.

In the case of Pretty Seakamela and her fellow artisanal miners, this is exemplified by their preferred method of gold extraction.²⁶ At the mining dump, in fact, they can practice two. The first involves digging and washing gravel. The second, instead, centers around crushing rocks. As they reveal during the site visit, the women have a preference for the latter. Crushing rocks is, in fact, less physically demanding than shoveling and transporting heavy buckets of gravel. It is also an individual, rather than a team activity, which means that revenues are not shared, and depend on the amount of work each miner is willing to put in. Most importantly, however, rocks can be easily transported back to the township and crushed at home, allowing women to attend to their other responsibilities, including house and care work.

Nozipho Mogotsi also appreciates the flexibility of her schedule. She relies, in fact, on a mix of hustling and state grants to survive, which can be easily combined with childrearing and her studies. This is perhaps the main reason why she is not sure if she really wants a salaried job. "I don't like the idea of being away for many hours and be paid by someone else. I prefer to have my own schedule", she explains during here interview.²⁷

The appreciation for flexibility expressed by Nozipho and the women artisanal miners reflects the struggles that women face in juggling their different roles. While expected to provide for their families, in fact, women also carry the greatest load in terms of reproductive work.

This is clearly exemplified by the case of ambitious Lesego Kunutu, who faces her own challenges balancing her business with her other responsibilities. During her interview, she shares that while preparing for her day at work, she typically also has to ensure that her children are ready for school. This usually means preparing breakfast and warming

up a bath. At 12pm, she is then expected to come back to welcome the children home after school and take care of the house. Recently, however, she has decided to employ a domestic worker to manage cleaning and other household chores, as she lacks the time to perform these tasks herself. This has caused her to get into fights with her husband, who complains that she attends more her business than her house and care responsibilities.

Balancing all responsibilities is particularly challenging for women raising children on their own, which, as discussed in previous sections, is not uncommon in the visited mining-affected communities. A hustler interviewed in Northern Cape has made a living out of this²⁸. She has become, in fact, a full-time nanny for her neighbor, who works at a fast-food restaurant in town. She looks after her newborn day and night, which earns her around 1500 ZAR per month. The other women in her community envy her for having found such a lucrative and relatively stable hustle, but she complains that the remuneration does not commensurate the huge workload that raising a child implies.

The challenges that women experience in relation to their gendered responsibilities are central in conversations about mining. Large-scale operations often increase, in fact, women's reproductive work load. This is made abundantly clear by an elderly woman living next to a coal mine in Mpumalanga.²⁹ During a focus group discussion, she describes how frustrating it is to do laundry in her community, where the dust generated by mining activities make the clothes dirty as soon as their hanged to dry. She complains that, as a result, she often has to wash the same clothes multiple times in the same day.

Women express similar grievances in communities where mining reduces access to clean water, typically located in more rural areas, like those in Northern Cape and Free State. Fetching water is, in fact, a gendered responsibility which disproportionately burdens women. During a workshop in Northern Cape, research participants have been particularly vocal about this issue. Many of them have complained about being forced to walk long distances in order to find clean water, sometimes very late at night. Women in Free State say water scarcity becomes particularly problematic during funerals, when women are expected to cook large quantities of food over the course of several days.

Frustration is also expressed in relation to air and water pollution generated by mining activities, which have established negative health consequences, particularly on children. Typically, in fact, women are the primary caregivers for sick family members within the household.

"When someone is sick at home, anyone who is around helps but you can't trust men as much. Kids are better. When my mom is sick, my dad sometimes helps but he does not pay a lot of attention. I know my sons are going to take more care of their grandma when I am not there"³⁰

"My mom had six siblings who died and now all her nieces and nephews ask her for help but when she is sick, they don't come and help"³¹

Women's concerns about the health effects of mining also extend to education. During a workshop in Northern Cape, for instance, organizers have explained the impacts of manganese toxicity on cognitive development in early childhood. Women's reaction was strong. Many, in fact, have found the information disconcerting, especially as they are the ones who often have to compensate for the gaps in the state's underfunded education system by supporting their children's learning. Ultimately, managing their children's cognitive disorders would fall on them,

²⁸ Interview, Ga-Segonyana Local Municipality, 17 April 2023.

²⁹ Focus group discussion, Emalahleni Local Municipality, 25 April 2023.

³⁰ Focus group discussion, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 1 April 2023.

³¹ Site visit with women, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 1 April 2023.

²⁴ Interview, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 02 April 2023.

²⁵ Interview, Merafong City Local Municipality, 27 March 2023.

²⁶ Site visit to artisanal mining site, City of Ekurhuleni Metropolitan Municipality, 03 April 2023.

²⁷ Interview, Merafong City Local Municipality, 27 March 2023.

adding work to their already busy schedule.

6. Discussion

Centering everyday hustling practices, this research set out to explore the multiple and dynamic ways in which Black, working-class women navigate both challenges and opportunities in communities affected by large-scale mining. Analyzing the narratives of women who participated in this research, three recurring themes have emerged: (i) survival, (ii) autonomy, and (iii) caregiving responsibilities. These findings raise the question: what do these three themes bring to an understanding of extractivism from the perspective of different women living in mining-affected communities?

Despite efforts to redress historical inequalities in extractive industries, for instance through the introduction of gender quotas in the Mining Charter, women still experience significant exclusion in local mining economies. This finding aligns with the South African literature evidencing the limitations of gender sensitive mining policies (Kaggwa, 2020).

The first theme – *survival* – highlights the limited livelihood options available to Black, working-class women in communities where large-scale mining represents a dominant industry. Women in this research report, in fact, that while mining companies may represent a key source of business and employment at the local level, most of the opportunities they offer remain inaccessible to them. The barriers they face are many, including age restrictions, skill requirements, discrimination and corruption (particularly, in the form of “sex bribes”). Some of these barriers are more prominent in certain sectors compared to others. Notably, skill requirements are a more pressing concern in areas where mining is projected to attract sizeable investments, like in the platinum mining community visited in Limpopo.

In this context, hustling emerges first as a critical livelihood strategy which, together with state grant allocations, allows women like those who participated in this research to provide for themselves and their families. In some cases, hustling practices also enable women to capitalize on the presence of large-scale mining. Examples include Lesego Kunutu’s attempt to register her food shop as a vendor with the local mine, as well as the artisanal mining business started by a group of women who search for gold in the dumps of large mining companies. Even these practices, however, often remain limited in their ability to generate profits because of numerous barriers, including institutional (e.g. difficulties obtaining a license), and economic (e.g. capital to grow a business) ones.

Not only do women still experience significant exclusion in local mining economies, they also continue to shoulder most of the costs. The second theme – *autonomy* – highlights the uncertainty and insecurity exacerbated by large-scale mining in local communities, which particularly affects women. In line with previous research (Shackleton, 2020), findings have shown that mining can be very disruptive to local livelihoods. This is particularly true, for instance, in the case of gold mining, when excessive blasting, coupled with poor drainage systems, leads to the formation of dangerous sinkholes. Although mining companies are legally mandated, under Social and Labor Plans (SLPs), to contribute to local development, women interviewed in this research contend that these efforts are often insufficient to mitigate the adverse effects of resource extraction on health and the environment.

Black women’s higher vulnerability to the uncertain living conditions created by large-scale mining and the unreliability of mining companies’ initiatives is reflected in their experiences of motherhood. Women in this research, in fact, report a staggering lack of reliable support from both personal networks and state welfare systems, resulting in a profound sense of isolation as they strive to raise their children amid the precarious living conditions in their communities. In this context, hustling emerges as a powerful tool for emancipation, guaranteeing them the means to be independent and self-reliant. This is well exemplified by Koko Mantsha’s accounts of utilizing the income

generated from her hustling activities to cover her children’s healthcare needs, particularly when the emissions from the nearby mineral processing plant adversely affected their health.

In addition, the third theme – *caregiving responsibilities* – emphasizes the disproportionate burden that befalls women in communities affected by large-scale mining, as found in previous research (Eftimie et al., 2009). Accounts from several women in this research detail, in fact, the added reproductive workload resulting from the negative impacts of mining, particularly in rural areas. These include dusty air that makes local residents sick and in need of care, as well as excessive toxicity in water that can result in chronic health conditions and stunt children’s cognitive development. As women are called to fill in the gaps left by weak state support systems and are expected to shoulder most care work, hustling provides them with the means to earn an income while retaining the flexibility needed to juggle their different responsibilities.

7. Conclusion

In South Africa, extractivism has driven the development agenda since the discovery of the country’s mineral wealth in the 1800s. Throughout much of this history, Black women have been confined to the edges. This study has set out to re-center their narratives in current debates of extractivism and development, by shedding light on their lived experiences of large-scale resource extraction. Through the lens of hustle lifeways, the research has focused in particular on exploring the multiple and dynamic ways in which Black, working-class women navigate the challenges and opportunities posed by industrial mining in their communities. In doing so, it contributes to the literature on mining and women, by providing insights into the livelihood strategies of women living in mining-affected communities without being necessarily employed in the sector.

Data for this study has been gathered following an ethnographic approach over a fieldwork period of three months, across different mining-affected communities of South Africa. Methods used during data collection include interviews, participant observation, focus group discussions and site visits. Information has been then thematically analyzed.

Throughout the analysis, three themes have emerged: survival, autonomy and caregiving responsibilities. These themes evidence the resourcefulness of Black women in this research, while underscoring the numerous challenges they face in their communities dominated by mining, particularly in terms of uncertainty and added care work.

The analysis of these three themes makes important contributions to the literature on mining in South Africa. First, it highlights the persistent exclusion faced by Black, working-class women in local mining economies, even in the context of gender-sensitive policies. This finding supports previous research on the limitations of such policies in addressing structural inequalities (Kaggwa, 2020). Secondly, findings shed light on the adverse effects of large-scale mining on local livelihoods. While Shackleton (2020) has documented the consequences of mining in terms of land dispossession and increased household vulnerability, this analysis extends the discussion by focusing on how these impacts disproportionately affect women. Finally, the analysis contributes to the growing body of literature on the burden of care work that falls on women due to mining’s negative impacts (Eftimie et al., 2009).

Beyond its contributions to the literature on gender and mining, the findings offer critical insights into broader debates on extractivism and development. The analysis shows that large-scale resource extraction, even when accompanied by gender-sensitive policies, does not automatically lead to improved gender equality. Instead, it reveals that extractivist development models may exacerbate existing inequalities, particularly for Black, working-class women, whose lived experiences are shaped by overlapping structures of race, class, and gender-based oppression.

In conclusion, this study argues that efforts to build just and sustainable pathways to development through mining require a more

radical and intersectional approach, centering the experiences of those who stand to gain the least and lose the most from extractive activities. It is only by foregrounding the perspectives of these marginalized individuals, like Black working-class women, that complex challenges inherent of extractive industries can be addressed.

The concept of hustle lifeways serves as an important analytical tool, offering valuable insights into the lived experiences of people in mining-affected communities. Incorporating the study of hustle lifeways into future research on extractivism and development will ensure a deeper, more nuanced understanding of mining's impacts on local communities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Beatrice Gibertini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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